

HEALTH LITERACY ON HYPERTENSION AND DIABETES MELLITUS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This comparative study explores the health literacy of participants with hypertension and diabetes mellitus in barangays Patrocinio and Dela Paz, Cortes, Bohol, focusing on demographic profiles and health literacy dimensions. Utilizing a quantitative comparative research design, data was collected through a self-made questionnaire. The study aimed to address specific research questions regarding demographic profiles, health literacy levels, significant differences in health literacy based on demographic factors, and recommendations based on findings. Findings reveal that while participants in both barangays displayed positive functional, communication, and analysis health literacy regarding hypertension and diabetes mellitus, challenges were observed in reading health literacy. Significant differences were noted in health literacy levels, particularly in barangay Dela Paz, related to education and income levels. Recommendations include tailored health education programs, interventions to enhance reading health literacy, strengthening communication skills, addressing socioeconomic disparities, targeted interventions for analysis health literacy, and continued monitoring and evaluation. These findings highlight the importance of addressing demographic variations and socioeconomic disparities in health literacy to promote better health outcomes in the community. Efforts to enhance health literacy should be tailored to meet the specific needs of participants, focusing on accessibility, comprehension, and empowerment in managing health conditions effectively. Continued monitoring and evaluation are essential for tracking progress and refining interventions to address emerging needs in promoting health literacy and improving health outcomes.

Keywords: *Demographic profiles, Diabetes mellitus, Health literacy, Hypertension, Monitoring and evaluation, Socioeconomic disparities*

INTRODUCTION

Health literacy is the ability to get and process health information or services to reach an appropriate health decision. A very important determinant of the client's ability to health self-care. Health maintenance, to at least functioning level, demands a general health literacy skill. These may include seeking treatment, interacting with the health care providers and navigating health care services available in the community. Health literacy helps understand how our body works and how lifestyle prevents or promotes morbidity. It affords the people the ability to develop skills to decide for the betterment of one's health as well as of the family.

Health literacy includes print literacy, oral literacy, numeracy skills, functional literacy, analysis literacy and the ability to use this information as a functioning health care consumer. Print literacy is needed to understand most of the education offered to the clients. The client's ability to communicate with the health care providers on their understanding, needs, concerns, and issue depends on the client's oral literacy. Numeracy literacy is needed in determining medicine calibration, dosage, and timing. The previously mentioned literacies will facilitate the client's functional literacy in seeking, analyzing, and using this information for self-care (Westlake, et al., 2013).

Health care consumers obtain most of health information from their engagement with the health care providers, health promotion advertisements, and various forms of health communications common in the community. This information is relied heavily in maintaining health of the families and the communities in general (Nielsen-Bohlman, et al., 2004). Thus, awareness of client's health literacy enables the health providers to make a tailored fit communication engagement with the clients, especially that health and health care services has spread outside the health care system. In a study conducted among the 402 hypertensive patients, ninety-two percent (92%) of patients having an adequate level of literacy knew that 160/100 mmHg blood pressure reading was high. While of the 114 patients diagnosed with diabetes, ninety-four percent (94%) of diabetic clients with functional health literacy were aware of the hypoglycemia symptoms. In one study, the result showed a persistent connection between low health literacy and poorer knowledge in diabetes self-care related management and were also true in cardiovascular and human immunodeficiency diseases (Laura Mackey et al., 2016). From the abovementioned studies, it can be deduced that low health literacy may influence negatively one's behavior in developing health management skills, thus, low health literacy is a legitimate health concern.

Another study revealed that clients with lower and adequate literacy were all interested in making medical decision. However, the big difference was their ability to ask medical questions. Clients with low literacy showed a lower medical questioning ability. (Aboumatar et al., 2013).

Filipinos' adherence to medication against heart and vascular diseases was reported to be as low as 66%, making heart and vascular diseases the leading causes of mortality

(Guitierrez and Sakubumrungsil, 2021). In the province of Bohol, hypertension figures consistently within the top 5 causes of morbidity despite its decreasing incidence from the year 2013 and 2014 with 15,392 and 13,922 incidences respectively. In the year 2015, hypertension total number of cases is 39,922 with morbidity rate of 2,555.69 and it ranked 2nd and 3rd in morbidity incidence in both females and males, respectively (PHO - Bohol, 2018). Although diabetes mellitus is not among the top ten morbidity diseases in the province of Bohol, still the data showed an increasing morbidity incidence. In 2013 and 2014, the total number of diabetes mellitus cases is 1,473 and 1,886 respectively, with morbidity rate of 113.03 in both years. In 2015, diabetes total number of cases is 2,382 with morbidity rate of 181.11. However, it increased by 50% in the year 2016. The total number of diabetes cases in this year is 4,695 with a morbidity rate of 353.72 (DOH - Bohol, 2018).

This study focused on health literacy of the participants having hypertension and diabetes. Particularly of the respondents' functional, reading, communication and analysis health literacy. This study showed the health literacy of the participants from barangay Dela Paz, which Holy Name University College of Nursing (HNU-CHS) had an immersion under the Community Health Nursing exposure, and in barangay Patrocinio, where the newly started immersion was halted due to the recent pandemic.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to compare the health literacy of the participants with hypertension and diabetes mellitus and specifically answer these questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of barangays Patrocinio and Dela Paz, Cortes, Bohol in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 Sex;
 - 1.2 Age;
 - 1.3 Education;
 - 1.4 Socio-economic status; and
 - 1.5 Health Condition?
2. What is the health literacy of the participants in terms of their:
 - 2.1 functional literacy;
 - 2.2 reading literacy;
 - 2.3 communicative literacy; and
 - 2.4 analysis literacy?
3. Is there a significant difference in the participants' health literacy in terms of their demographic profile?
4. What recommendations can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This section focused on the methodology that was utilized in the conduct of the study. This also outlined the research design, the procedure that was followed, the

process of collecting the data and the analysis. During the collection process, the ethical consideration was also discussed.

Research Design

The study was a quantitative comparative research design comparing the health literacy of the participants and its relation to their demographic profile objectively through a numerical representation.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in barangays Dela Paz and Patrocinio, Cortes, Bohol. Cortes is a 5th class municipality based on the annual ranking of both cities and municipalities competitive index. Dela Paz is approximately 7.0 kilometers from Tagbilaran City and Patrocinio is 16.9 kilometers away. No such research in this nature has been done yet in both barangays. Barangay Dela Paz was the area of Community Health Nursing exposure of Holy Name University College of Health Sciences. While barangay Patrocinio of the same municipality was also an area of the mentioned exposure but was immediately stopped because of the pandemic.

Research Participants

The chosen participants of barangays Patrocinio and Dela Paz, Cortes, Bohol were the hypertensive and diabetic residents listed in Cortes Rural Health Office conferred by the respective Barangay Health Units personnel and who are still residing in the barangay and are still able and coherent. In barangay Patrocinio, the participants of the study were 28 solely hypertensive residents, 2 purely diabetic and 11 residents with hypertension and diabetes mellitus. This number was obtained after a calculation which yielded a 95% confidence level and 5% margin error from total population of 30 solely hypertensive, 2 purely diabetic and 11 residents having both conditions. Barangay Patrocinio have a total population of 855 residents (PSA, 2020). In barangay Dela Paz, the participants of the study were 41 solely hypertensive residents, 3 purely diabetic and 6 with hypertension and diabetes mellitus. This number was obtained after a calculation which yielded a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error from a total population of 50 solely hypertensive, 3 pure diabetic and 6 residents with both conditions. Barangay Dela Paz have a total population of 2,948 residents (PSA, 2020).

Research Instrument

The research instrument was a self-made questionnaire based on the concept of S-Test of Functional Health Literacy of Adults or S-TOFHLA (Parker, Baker, et al., 1995). And as cited by Emtekær Hæsum, L. K., Ehlers, L., & Hejlesen, O. K., 2015, Don Nutbeam divide S-TOFHLA into functional level, interactive level, and critical level.

Based on the above research, the undersigned researcher further made more divisions to make it a more simplified survey questionnaire without deviating from the concepts of the above-mentioned studies. However, numeracy and writing literacy was

not included in the study. The questionnaire Health Literacy on Hypertension and Diabetes Mellitus a Comparative study had two (2) parts. The demographic profile of the participants was the first part which included the respondent's sex, age, educational attainment, economic status, and health condition.

The second part covered the participants' health literacy and is divided into four subparts. The first subpart was the functional literacy. This part covered the participants' awareness related to the DOH program against hypertension and diabetes mellitus, sources of health information, healthy lifestyle practices information. This part also included the participants participation to the activities related to the DOH healthy lifestyle program and the actual engagement of the healthy lifestyle practices such as accessing the hypertension and diabetes mellitus medications and visits to health center for consultation.

The second subpart was questions related to the participants' reading literacy. In this study, the reading literacy refer to the factors that influenced the participants' capability to read and understand health instructions or information. These included the font size of the written health information or instructions, the used of words unknown to the participants, information that were hard to comprehend, the need to spent a longer time to read and understand the instructions or information and the need for other person to read and understand the instructions or information.

The third subpart assessed the participants' communication health literacy. These included the participants' actual sources of health information, ability to acquire the desired information, understanding of the information obtained, expression of ideas related to hypertension and diabetes mellitus, application of the obtained health information, the used of remote ways for health consultation such as telephone or cellphone and the used of social media platform for consultation.

The last part was the participants' analytical health literacy. This part assessed how they processed the information for better use. These included the participants' ability to weigh the information that were best applicable for their conditions, if they considered the credibility and veracity of the obtained information, if the collected information were used as the basis of their decisions and if they used the information in managing their conditions.

The Likert scale was used to determine the participants' agreeability with the statement: 1.00 - 1.80 = Strongly Disagreed; 1.81 - 2.60 = Disagreed, 2.61 - 3.40 = Doubtful; 3.41 - 4.20 = Agreed; 4.21 - 5.00 = Strongly Agreed.

The questionnaire for Health Literacy on Hypertension and Diabetes Mellitus A Comparative Study was validated through pilot-testing on 30 respondents from 3 barangays. The participants subjected for pilot-testing were not research participants nor residing in the research locale. The result was then validated by a statistician as to the questionnaire's reliability using Cronbach's Alpha N obtaining a result of 0.946, a high degree of reliability. The survey questionnaire was in Cebuano language.

RESULTS

Table 1. Participants' Demographic Profile

Demographic	Patrocinio		Dela Paz	
Sex	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Male	19	46	20	40.0
Female	22	54	30	60.0
Total	41	100.0	50	100.0
Age	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
28 - 35	0	0	2	4.0
36 – 43	2	5	3	6.0
44 - 51	10	24	6	12.0
52 - 59	8	20	13	26.0
60 and above	21	51	26	52.0
Total	41	100.0	50	100.0
Education	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
None	0	0	2	4.0
Elementary	21	51	20	40.0
High School	16	39	15	30.0
College	4	10	12	24.0
Postgraduate	0	0	1	2.0
Total	41	100.0	50	100.0
Income Per Month	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Below ₱ 5,000	29	71	39	78.0
₱ 5,001.00 - 10,000.00	7	17	9	18.0
₱ 10,001.00 - 15,000.00	4	10	2	4.0
₱ 15,001.00 - 20,000.00	1	2	0	0
₱ 20,001.00 & more	0	0	0	0
Total	41	100.0	50	100.0

Demographic	Patrocinio		Dela Paz	
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36 – 43	2	5	3	6.0
44 - 51	10	24	6	12.0
52 - 59	8	20	13	26.0
60 and above	21	51	26	52.0
Health Condition	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Hypertension only	28	68	41	82.0
Diabetes mellitus only	2	5	3	6.0
Hypertension and diabetes mellitus	11	27	6	12.0
Total	41	100.0	50	100.0

Table 2. Participants' Functional Health Literacy

Functional Health Literacy	Patrocinio		Dela Paz	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
Awareness				
Since being diagnosed with diabetes mellitus or hypertension or both, I became aware of the Healthy Lifestyle campaign of the DOH through its health workers, such as:	4.37	Strongly Agree	4.12	Agree
1.1. Diet planning (Pinggang Pinoy)				
1.2. Exercise	4.34	Strongly Agree	4.14	Agree
1.3. Smoke cessation and avoidance of the second-hand smokers.	4.34	Strongly Agree	4.22	Strongly Agree
2. I accessed the Healthy Lifestyle (HL) information of the Department Health through social media (facebook), TV, radio, internet and reading materials in the municipal health center.	3.34	Doubtful	3.74	Agree
3. I accessed the Healthy Lifestyle (HL) Information through the student nurses.	3.33	Doubtful	3.68	Agree
4. My awareness and consciousness of healthy lifestyle such as healthy diet and exercise increases.	4.02	Agree	4.08	Agree

Overall	3.95	Agree	3.99	Agree
Functional Health Literacy	Patrocinio		Dela Paz	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
Participation				
I participated in the healthy lifestyle activities promoted/conducted by the municipal health center personnel, such as:				
5.1. Diet planning (Pinggang Pinoy)	4.34	Strongly Agree	4.14	Agree
5.2. Exercise	4.37	Strongly Agree	4.12	Agree
5.3. Smoke cessation and avoidance of the second-hand smokers.	4.44	Strongly Agree	4.16	Agree
Overall	4.38	Strongly Agree	4.14	Agree
Practice				
6. I availed the low-cost medications for diabetes mellitus like metformin in the municipal health center.	4.00	Agree	3.33	Doubtful
7. I availed the low-cost medications for diabetes mellitus like metformin not from the municipal health center.	3.00	Doubtful	3.67	Agree
8. I availed the low-cost anti-hypertensive medications like losartan and amlodipine in the municipal health center.	3.64	Agree	3.69	Agree
9. I availed the low-cost anti-hypertensive medications like losartan and amlodipine not from the municipal health center.	3.82	Agree	3.90	Agree
10. I availed the low-cost medications for diabetes mellitus (metformin) and hypertension (losartan and amlodipine) in the municipal health center.	3.27	Doubtful	4.00	Agree

11. I availed the low-cost medications for diabetes mellitus (metformin) and hypertension (losartan and amlodipine) not from the municipal health center.	3.27	Doubtful	3.80	Agree
12. I practice the activities related to healthy lifestyle thought by the municipal health center personnel.	3.61	Agree	3.88	Agree
Functional Health Literacy Practice	Patrocinio		Dela Paz	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
13. I practice the activities related to healthy lifestyle thought by the student's nurses	3.39	Doubtful	3.86	Agree
14. I sought health consultation in the municipal health center.	3.56	Agree	3.52	Agree
15. I sought health consultation not in the municipal health center.	3.00	Doubtful	3.72	Agree
Overall	3.45	Agree	3.73	Agree
Overall Total	3.92	Agree	3.95	Agree

Interval

1.00 – 1.80
1.81 – 2.60
2.61 – 3.40
3.41 – 4.20
4.21 – 5.00

Qualitative Description

Strongly Disagree
Disagree
Doubtful
Agree
Strongly Agree

In Table 2, the participants of both barangays had obtained the same agreement as to the awareness of the functional health literacy. Participants of barangays Patrocinio and Dela Paz had garnered a mean of 3.95 and 3.99 respectively, qualitatively described as agreed. As to their participation on the functional health literacy, the participants from barangay Patrocinio had obtained a higher functional health literacy, getting a mean of 4.38 which is qualitatively described as strongly agreed while the participants in barangay Dela Paz had obtained only a mean of 4.14, qualitatively described as agreed. To the participants' practice of the functional health, both barangays had obtained the same agreement thereto. Participants of barangay Patrocinio had garnered a mean of 3.45 and for Dela Paz 3.73, both qualitatively described as agreed.

Thus, the participants of both barangays obtained a total overall mean of 3.92 and 3.95, qualitatively described as agreed. Thus, they were aware, had participated on the health programs, availed the medications and sought health consultations. Westlake et al., 2013, in their study mentioned that among others, the ability to use health information will facilitate the client's functional literacy.

Table 3. Participants' Reading Health Literacy

Reading Health Literacy	Patrocinio		Dela Paz	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
In reading instructions or leaflets from the municipal health center, other health practitioner and pharmacies, 1. I found that the print was too small to read.	3.83	Agree	3.70	Agree
2. I found characters and words that I did not know.	3.71	Agree	3.68	Agree
3. I found that the content was too difficult to understand.	3.71	Agree	3.72	Agree
4. I needed a longer time to read and understand it.	3.78	Agree	3.82	Agree
5. I needed someone to help me read and understand it.	4.00	Agree	3.70	Agree
Overall	3.80	Agree	3.72	Agree

Table 3 reflects that the participants of both barangays had acquired a qualitative description of agreement to the statement pertaining to reading health literacy. The above result showed an overall mean of 3.80 for Patrocinio and 3.72 for Dela Paz, therefore, these participants did experience a degree of difficulty in reading and understanding the instructions which were impediments to improve one's overall health literacy. It is noticeable, however, that a greater number of participants from barangay Patrocinio needs somebody to read and help them understand the instructions or reading materials. This may correlate to the educational profile of Patrocinio in which 51% of the participants only had attained elementary schooling.

According to Bryant, A. 2012, health literacy as defined by the Institute of Medicine is not simply being able to read but also on the individual's capacity to process and understand the obtained health information. Simply put, it means the person's capacity to read, listen, analyze and decide in relation to one's health. In this study, the respondents of barangay Patrocinio and Dela Paz were not only asked as to the degree of their

difficulty in reading health instructions but were also asked as to whether or not they understood the printed instructions.

Table 4. Participants' Communication Health Literacy

Communication Literacy	Patrocinio		Dela Paz	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
Since being diagnosed with diabetes mellitus or hypertension or both, 1. I have collected information from various sources.	3.54	Agree	4.00	Agree
Communication Literacy	Patrocinio		Dela Paz	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
2. I have extracted information I wanted related to hypertension and diabetes mellitus.	3.85	Agree	3.92	Agree
3. I have understood the obtained information.	4.00	Agree	3.92	Agree
3. I have communicated my thoughts of having diabetes mellitus to someone.	4.00	Agree	4.00	Agree
4. I have communicated my thoughts of having diabetes mellitus to someone.	4.00	Agree	4.00	Agree
5. I have communicated my thoughts of having hypertension to someone.	3.93	Agree	4.12	Agree
6. I have communicated my thoughts of having hypertension and diabetes mellitus to someone.	3.58	Agree	4.00	Agree
7. I have communicated that I applied the obtained information to my daily life.	3.83	Agree	4.02	Agree

8. I have used my phone (call and text), when consulting with a physician, nurse, midwife, BHW in the municipal health center.	3.05	Doubtful	3.66	Agree
9. I have used my phone (call and text), when consulting with a physician, nurse, or midwife not from the municipal health center.	2.85	Doubtful	3.48	Agree
10. I have used my facebook/messenger when consulting with physician, nurse, midwife, BHW in the municipal health center.	2.66	Doubtful	3.36	Doubtful
11. I have used my facebook/messenger when consulting with physician, nurse, midwife not from the municipal health center.	2.46	Disagree	3.30	Doubtful
Overall	3.43	Agree	3.79	Agree

Table 4 shows that the participants of both barangays came into agreement of having positively sourced, acquired, understood, and communicated their thoughts and applied the information in their daily lives. Nonetheless, the participants differ in their response as to the use of their phone, call or text, in seeking consultation from or not from the municipal physician, nurse, midwife and BHW. Respondents from Patrocinio obtained a mean of 3.05 and 2.85 in these areas which is qualitatively described as doubtful. On the other hand, participants of barangay Dela Paz had garnered a mean of 3.66 and 3.48 in these areas, qualitatively described as agreed. Thus, the participants of Dela Paz were more adaptive in utilizing their phone for call or text in communicating or contacting their health workers. This is also true to the statement referring to the use of facebook/messenger in seeking consultation from the physician, nurse and midwife not from municipal health center. Respondents from Patrocinio had disagreed on the utilization of this application having a mean of 2.46 or is qualitatively described as disagreed. On the same parameter, the respondents of barangay Dela Paz obtained a mean of 3.30, qualitatively described as doubtful. Thus, the participants of Dela Paz were more adaptive in utilizing their facebook/messenger in communicating or contacting health workers not from the municipal health center. Thus, although both barangays have a positive overall communication health literacy, it is to some degree higher among the respondents from Dela Paz.

Communication health literacy is the ability to obtain meaningful health information from different sources or forms of communication. In a study conducted by Machiko Inoue et al., 2013, the result revealed that clear client-physician communication line and critical

health literacy were independently associated with the client's understanding of diabetes self-efficacy and care. Communication line and education of clients with diabetes in primary care setting should be considered.

Table 5. Participants' Analysis Health Literacy

Analysis Health Literacy	Patrocinio		Dela Paz	
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description
Since being diagnosed with diabetes mellitus or hypertension or both 1. I have considered whether the information was applicable to my situation having diabetes mellitus.	4.00	Agree	3.67	Agree
2. I have considered whether the information was applicable to my situation having hypertension.	3.93	Agree	3.93	Agree
3. I have considered whether the information was applicable to my situation having diabetes and hypertension.	4.09	Agree	4.00	Agree
4. I have considered the credibility of the source of information.	3.88	Agree	4.06	Agree
5. I have considered whether the information was valid and reliable.	3.88	Agree	3.98	Agree
6. I have collected information to make health-related decisions.	3.93	Agree	4.06	Agree
7. I have used such information to manage myself as a diabetic person.	4.50	Strongly Agree	3.67	Agree
8. I have used such information to manage myself as a hypertensive person.	4.37	Strongly Agree	4.05	Agree
9. I have used such information to manage myself as a hypertensive and diabetic person.	4.42	Strongly Agree	4.33	Agree
Overall	4.11	Agree	3.97	Agree

As reflected in Table 5, the participants of both barangays obtained a positive analysis health literacy in all 9 statements, obtaining an overall mean of 4.11 in Patrocino and 3.97 in Dela Paz. Thus, they had analyzed and considered the credibility, validity and reliability of the information as well. However, it is noticeable that the participants of barangay Patrocino, to some degree, have a better analysis health literacy compared to its counterpart. This is in the participants' utilization of the information to manage themselves having hypertension, diabetes or having both, obtaining a mean qualitatively described as strongly agreed.

According to Bryant, A., 2012, health literacy as defined by the Institute of Medicine is not simply being able to read but also on the individual's capacity to process and understand the obtained health information. Simply put, it is the person's capacity to read, listen, analyze and decide related to one's health. Obtaining a mean qualitatively described as agreed shows that respondents of both barangays had understood, analyzed and used the information to manage their health conditions.

Table 6. Difference of Participants' Health Literacy in Terms of their Sex

Health Literacy (Sex) t-test Independent Samples	Patrocion			Dela Paz		
	t-value	p-value	Decision	t-value	p-value	Decision
Functional Health Literacy	1.333	0.190	Accept H _o	0.605	0.548	Accept H _o
Reading Health Literacy	0.624	0.536	Accept H _o	0.060	0.952	Accept H _o
Communication Health Literacy	0.031	0.976	Accept H _o	0.208	0.836	Accept H _o
Analysis Health Literacy	0.526	0.602	Accept H _o	3.262	0.002	Reject H _o

As shown in the table 6, participants of both barangays had accepted the hypothesis of no significant difference on their functional, reading, and communication health literacy in terms of their sex. Thus, in both barangays, the participants' functional and communicative health literacy have no relationship nor did they differ as far as their sex is concerned. The same with their experience of having difficulty in reading and understanding the health materials from municipal center or pharmacy. However, this is not true to the analysis health literacy, as while Patrocino participants accepted the hypothesis, participants in barangay Dela Paz had rejected the same.

Thus, Dela Paz shows a significant difference of the participants' analysis health literacy in terms of their sex. It is noted that 60% of the respondents from Dela Paz were women. In a study that was conducted by Dhar, S et al, 2019, which focused on groups of different ages, nativity, and gender and asked on their opinion of the specific topics,

result shows that among others, diabetes and hypertension were the primary concern and the women were more concerned about the family's health and dietary habits.

The result in Dela Paz rejecting the hypothesis in analysis health literacy in relation to sex may correlate to the study of Das, S. et al., 2017, that in knowledge of diabetes control, females at 44.4% knew more than males at 36.6%. Same with hypertension, in which 31.1% of females have knowledge about it compared to the 24.2% knowledge of its male counterpart.

Table 7. Difference of Participants' Health Literacy in Terms of their Age

Health Literacy (Age) ANOVA	Patrocinio			Dela Paz		
	F-value	p-value	Decision	F-value	p-value	Decision
Functional Health Literacy	.252	.907	Accept H _o	0.869	0.446	Accept H _o
Reading Health Literacy	1.046	.394	Accept H _o	0.167	0.918	Accept H _o
Communication Health Literacy	1.505	.217	Accept H _o	0.842	0.480	Accept H _o
Analysis Health Literacy	1.157	.342	Accept H _o	1.137	0.347	Accept H _o

Table 7 reflects that participants in both barangays had accepted the hypothesis of no significant difference of their functional, reading, communication and analysis health literacy in relation to their age. Thus, the participants' awareness, participation of the health program and adherence to healthy practices have no relationship nor did they differ as to their age. The same is true as to their ability to collect, extract, understand and communicate information related to hypertension and diabetes mellitus. Likewise, their ability to consider the applicability, credibility, validity, reliability of the information have no bearing as far as their age is concerned.

In a study of Fırat Kılıç, et al., 2023, "The Relationship Between Successful Aging and Health Literacy in Older Adults", it showed that health literacy is negatively correlated with age. Also, in a study conducted by Kozar Westmen, et al., 2019 in Northern Carolina, the result concluded that there is no significant difference between age and successful aging perception.

Table 8. Difference of Participants' Health Literacy in Terms of their Education

Health Literacy (Education) ANOVA	Patrocinio			Dela Paz		
	F-value	p-value	Decision	F-value	p-value	Decision
Functional Health Literacy	0.044	0.957	Accept H _o	3.528	0.014	Reject H _o
Reading Health Literacy	0.164	0.849	Accept H _o	3.530	0.014	Reject H _o
Communication Health Literacy	1.411	0.256	Accept H _o	2.007	0.110	Accept H _o
Analysis Health Literacy	0.955	0.394	Accept H _o	1.122	0.358	Accept H _o

Table 8 shows that while the participants in barangay Patrocinio accepted the hypothesis of no significant difference as to their functional, reading, communicative and analysis health literacy in relation to their education, the same is not true in barangay Dela Paz, for it rejected the hypothesis as far as to their functional and reading health literacy. Fifty six percent (56%) of the participants from Dela Paz had either attended high school, college or post-graduate school compared to only 49% of the participants from barangay Patrocinio who had either gone to high school or college. Thus, the participants of Dela Paz had experienced less burden in reading and understanding the health materials from the municipal center or from the pharmacy. This data is relevant to the study conducted by Mark V William MD et. al., 2007, which shows that ninety-two percent (92%) of the hypertensive patient with adequate level of literacy knew that 160/100 mmHg blood pressure reading was high. Functional and reading health literacy is very important in knowing health programs, sourcing health information and in engaging with the health practitioners.

The domain of information sufficiency to manage personal health actively, ability to source for appropriate information were positively associated with educational attainment. Thus, poor cognition and the lower the educational attainment is detrimental to the functional literacy on an individual. Furthermore, low education, diabetes distress and older age were detrimental in multiple health literacy domains (Chen, P. et al., 2022).

Table 9. Difference in the Health Literacy of the Participants in Terms of their Monthly Income

Health Literacy (Income per Month) ANOVA	Patrocinio			Dela Paz		
	F-value	p-value	Decision	F-value	p-value	Decision
Functional Health Literacy	0.246	0.863	Accept H _o	1.056	0.356	Accept H _o
Reading Health Literacy	0.595	0.622	Accept H _o	15.076	0.000	Reject H _o
Communication Health Literacy	0.922	0.440	Accept H _o	1.473	0.240	Accept H _o
Analysis Health Literacy	2.171	0.108	Accept H _o	1.868	0.166	Accept H _o

Table 9 shows that the participants of both barangays accepted the hypothesis of no significant difference in their health literacy in terms of their income per month. Thus, the participants' awareness, participation of the health program and adherence to healthy practices have no relationship nor difference as far as their monthly income is concerned. The same is true as to their ability to collect, extract, understand and communicate information related to hypertension and diabetes mellitus. Likewise, their ability to consider the applicability, credibility, validity, reliability of the information have no bearing as to their monthly income. However, participants from barangay Dela Paz rejected the hypothesis in terms of their reading health literacy. In barangay Dela Paz, despite their low income, 56% of the participants had gone to high school, college, or post-graduate school, thus, rejecting the hypothesis. Thus, participants of barangay Dela Paz experienced less burden in reading and understanding the health materials. As mentioned by Fırat Kılıç, et al., 2023, as the education levels increased, health literacy also increases.

Table 10. Difference of Participants' Health Literacy in Terms of their Health Condition

Health Literacy (Health Condition) Kruskal-Wallis H	Patrocinio			Dela Paz		
	Chi-Squared	p-value	Decision	Chi-Squared	p-value	Decision
Functional Health Literacy	8.522	0.014	Accept H _o	3.861	0.145	Accept H _o
Reading Health Literacy	0.414	0.813	Accept H _o	2.313	0.315	Accept H _o
Communication Health Literacy	1.041	0.496	Accept H _o	5.964	0.051	Reject H _o
Analysis Health Literacy	2.222	0.329	Accept H _o	1.270	0.530	Accept H _o

As depicted in Table 10, the participants of both barangays accepted the hypothesis of no significant difference on their health literacy in relation to their health condition, except for barangay Dela Paz which rejected the hypothesis in terms of their communication health literacy. In previous table showing results in the functional health literacy, specifically table 2, participants from Dela Paz sought consults not only from the health professionals in the municipal health center but also from health professionals not working within. Thus, in addition to their education profile, Dela Paz participants are more engaged and conversant as to their condition. The data is in line with the study conducted by Aboumatar et al., 2013, which showed the influence of health literacy in making medical visit, healthcare participation, communication engagement during visit, and the purported visit outcomes in their ability to ask medical questions. Clients with low literacy shows a lower medical questioning ability and have limited capacity to communicate with the health care providers using patient-centered approaches of engagement. In this study, communicative health literacy refers to the respondent's ability to acquire, ask and express thoughts or ideas related to their health conditions.

Findings

Based on the results of the statistical analysis and treatment of the gathered data, the following findings were obtained:

1. Participants Demographic Profile:

Most of the participants of both barangays were female and majority were above 60 years of age. In barangay Patrocinio, fifty-one percent (51%) of the participants attained an elementary schooling at the very least. While in barangay Dela Paz, twenty-four percent (24%) of the participants had a college education compare to ten percent (10%) from barangay Patrocinio. For the income, majority of the participants in both barangays had a monthly income of less than ₱5,000.00. Majority of them were solely hypertensive.

2. Participants' Health Literacy:

Participants of both barangays had obtained a qualitative description of agreed for functional health literacy, which suggests that they were aware of, and had participated on activities related to the health programs, as well as had availed the medications and had sought health consultations. For reading health literacy, participants of both barangays had obtained a qualitative description of agreed which means that they had experienced a certain degree of difficulty in reading and understanding the instructions.

Likewise, participants of both barangays had obtained a qualitative description of agreed for communication health literacy which signifies that participants had extracted, collected, understood, and applied the information and had communicated their thoughts regarding their health condition to others. For analysis health literacy, the participants of both barangays had obtained a qualitative description of agreed for analysis health literacy. Thus, participants had understood, analyzed and used the information to manage their health conditions.

3. Significant Difference on the Participants Health Literacy and Demographic Profile:

Participant from barangay Patrocino totally accepted the hypothesis of no significant difference on hypertension and diabetes mellitus health literacy in relation to their sex, age, education, income per month and health condition. However, participants from Dela Paz rejected the hypothesis in the following: analysis health literacy in relation to their sex; functional health literacy in relation to their education; reading health literacy in relation to their education and income; and communication health literacy in relation to their health condition.

Conclusions

The findings had reflected that the participants of both barangays agreed that they had positive hypertension and diabetes mellitus functional, communication, and analysis health literacy. The health programs and activities to address the incidence of hypertension and diabetes mellitus in placed by the Department of Health as implemented by the municipal health workers of Cortes, Bohol is positively working in barangays Dela Paz and Patrocino. The health education, the health related activities, the availability of the essential medication and services against hypertension and diabetes mellitus had led the participants to perform the healthy lifestyle and practices. This positive behavior was further supported by the available health services from the private health sectors and the student nurses. To further enhance the current good hypertension and diabetes mellitus health literacy of the participants to a wellness state, a supported program should be in place to help and support the participants to improve their reading and understanding difficulty. Also, a good remote communication lines should be established between the health providers and the participants and to teach and encourage the latter how to use the same.

Recommendations

Pursuant to the conclusion based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Tailored Health Education Programs

Recognizing the demographic characteristics of the participants, particularly the predominance of females and individuals above 60 years of age, health education programs should be tailored to meet the specific needs of these demographic groups. Efforts should focus on providing accessible and easily understandable health information to cater to the diverse educational backgrounds observed, ranging from elementary schooling to college education.

2. Enhancing Reading Health Literacy

Given that participants in both barangays experienced difficulty in reading and understanding health instructions, interventions aimed at improving reading health literacy are imperative. This could include the development of simplified health materials, the provision of audiovisual aids, and the implementation of literacy-enhancing strategies to facilitate comprehension.

3. Strengthening Communication Skills

Despite participants demonstrating adequate communication health literacy, efforts should be made to further strengthen their communication skills regarding their health conditions. Health providers should encourage open dialogue, actively listen to participants' concerns, and foster an environment where individuals feel empowered to express their health-related needs and preferences.

4. Addressing Disparities in Education and Income

The significant differences observed in health literacy, particularly in relation to education and income levels in barangay Dela Paz, underscore the importance of addressing socioeconomic disparities. Initiatives aimed at improving access to education and economic opportunities can contribute to enhancing health literacy levels and promoting better health outcomes in the community.

5. Targeted Interventions for Analysis Health Literacy

Given the unanimous agreement on analysis health literacy among participants in both barangays, interventions should focus on further enhancing participants' abilities to understand, analyze, and utilize health information to manage their health conditions effectively. This could involve providing additional training on health data interpretation, encouraging critical thinking skills, and facilitating access to resources for informed decision-making.

6. Continued Monitoring and Evaluation

Regular monitoring and evaluation of health literacy levels and demographic profiles of participants are essential to track progress and identify areas for improvement.

Ongoing assessment can inform the development and refinement of targeted interventions to address emerging needs and challenges in promoting health literacy and improving health outcomes in the community.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

All ethical criteria were considered in conducting this study. The research topics were not sensitive nor did it place the participants and the institution at any risk. Participation was at all times voluntary. They were invited to participate by explaining to them the objectives and the informed consent of the study. After they expressed their consent and after affixing their signature or thumbmark, the questionnaire was explained to them. The participants participated by either answering the interviewer or they themselves read and wrote their answer. They were informed of their right to withdraw at any moment without the need for an explanation. The researcher employed the appropriate measures during the interaction with the participants, in collecting data or responses, and during analyzing of the gathered data. The participants were assured on the confidentiality of their identity and answers, they were also assured that the answered questionnaires can be accessed only by the researcher or the concerned barangay health workers. The benefits of the study were also explained as described in the significance of the study. The research was in conformity to the Holy Name University Ethics Review Board (HNU-ERB) standards. Approval from the HNU-ERB was sought prior to the data collection. The researchers declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

REFERENCES

- Aboumatar, Hanan, Kathryn Carson, Mary Beach, Debra Roter, and Lisa Cooper. (2013). The Impact of Health Literacy on Desire for Participation in Healthcare, Medical Visit Communication, and Patient Reported Outcomes among Patients with Hypertension at JGIM: *Journal of General Internal Medicine* 28 (11): 1469–76. doi:10.1007/s11606-013-2466-5 on July 16, 2022
- Bryant, A. (2012). Development of guidelines for the selection of appropriate reading material for clients with low health literacy. *JOCEPS: The Journal of Chi Eta Phi Sorority*, 56(1), 17–20 at <https://search-ebshost-com.hnulrc.idm.oclc.org/login.aspx?direct=true&db=rzh&AN=104156601&site=ehost-live> on August 13, 2022
- Chen, P., Callisaya, M., Wills, K., Greenaway, T., & Winzenberg, T. (2022). Cognition, educational attainment and diabetes distress predict poor health literacy in diabetes: A cross-sectional analysis of the SHELLED study. *PLoS ONE*, 17(4), 1–12 at <https://doi-org.hnulrc.idm.oclc.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0267265> on July 20, 2022
- Das, S., Mia, M. N., Ahmed Hanifi, S. M., Hoque, S., Bhuiya, A., & Hanifi, S. M. A. (2017). Health literacy in a community with low levels of education: findings from Chakaria, a rural area of Bangladesh. *BMC Public Health*, 17, 1–10. <https://doi-org.hnulrc.idm.oclc.org/10.1186/s12889-017-4097-y> on July 20, 2022
- Dhar, S., Pande, M., Gor, B., Banerjee, D., Krishnan, S., Dorai, V. K., Kabad, K., Jones, L., Naik, L. R., & Legha, S. S. (2019). Differences in nativity, age and gender may impact

- health behavior and perspectives among Asian Indians. *Ethnicity & Health*, 24(5), 484–494 at <https://doi-org.hnulrc.idm.oclc.org/10.1080/13557858.2017.1346783> on August 13, 2022
- Emtekær Hæsum, L. K., Ehlers, L., & Hejlesen, O. K. (2015). Validation of the Test of Functional Health Literacy in Adults in a Danish population. *Scandinavian Journal of Caring Sciences*, 29(3), 573–581 at <https://doi-org.hnulrc.idm.oclc.org/10.1111/scs.12186> on July 30, 2022
- Kautzky-Willer, A., Dorner, T., Jensby, A., & Rieder, A. (2012). Women show a closer association between educational level and hypertension or diabetes mellitus than males: a secondary analysis from the Austrian HIS. *BMC Public Health*, 12(1), 392 at <https://doi-org.hnulrc.idm.oclc.org/10.1186/1471-2458-12-392> on August 13, 2022
- Laura M. Mackey; Catherine Doody; and Erik L, Werner (2016) “Self-Management Skills in Chronic Disease Management: What Role Does Health Literacy Have? at <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0272989X16638330> on July 13, 2022
- Machiko Inoue, Miyako Takahashi, & Ichiro Kai. (2013). Impact of communicative and critical health literacy on understanding of diabetes care and self-efficacy in diabetes management: a cross-sectional study of primary care in Japan. *BMC Family Practice*, 14(1), 40–48 at <https://doi-org.hnulrc.idm.oclc.org/10.1186/1471-2296-14-40> on August, 13, 2022
- M. Kozar Westman, M. Troutman Jordan, and M. A. Nies, (2013). Successful aging among assisted living community older adults at *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 238–246, 2013/ <https://sigmapubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/jnu.12027> on August 13, 2022.
- Nutbeam, D. (2000). Health literacy as a public health goal: a challenge for contemporary health education and communication strategies into the 21st century. *Health Promotion International*, 15(3), 259–267 at <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapro/15.3.259> on July 19, 2022
- Tang, K., Zhang, Y., Wang, H., Tan, S. H., Bai, L., & Liu, Y. (2020). Regional economic development, household income, gender and hypertension: evidence from half a million Chinese. *BMC Public Health*, 20(1), 1–12 at <https://doi-org.hnulrc.idm.oclc.org/10.1186/s12889-020-09002-y> on August 13, 2022
- Zhang, Y., Yang, H., Ren, M., Wang, R., Zhao, F., Liu, T., Zhang, Y., Guo, Z., & Cong, H. (2021). Distribution of risk factors of hypertension patients in different age groups in Tianjin. *BMC Public Health*, 21(1), 1–10. <https://doi-org.hnulrc.idm.oclc.org/10.1186/s12889-021-10250-9> Women show a closer association between educational level and hypertension or diabetes mellitus than males: a secondary analysis from the Austrian HIS. (2012). *BMC Public Health*, 12(1), 392–400 at <https://doi-org.hnulrc.idm.oclc.org/10.1186/1471-2458-12-39> on August 13, 2022